

This document includes detailed tables of the impact of selection bias effect η and linear time trend effect θ separately and jointly on the type I error probability for different randomization procedures.

Table 1: Impact of selection bias effect $\eta = 0.09$ and linear time trend effect $\theta = 0.26$ with $\sigma = 0.73$ on probability of type I error for different randomization procedures

Randomization Procedure [<i>RP</i>]	Type I Error Probability [mean]	$P_{RP}(\omega \leq 0.05)$
CR	0.050	0.53
RAR	0.052	0.34
PBR(2)	0.105	0.00
PBR(10)	0.069	0.00
BSD(3)	0.054	0.11
BSD(4)	0.052	0.34
BSD(5)	0.051	0.46
MP(3)	0.062	0.00
MP(4)	0.058	0.01
MP(5)	0.055	0.06
EBC(0.67)	0.062	0.02
CHEN(2, 0.67)	0.072	0.00
CHEN(3, 0.67)	0.066	0.00
CHEN(4, 0.67)	0.064	0.00
CHEN(5, 0.67)	0.063	0.01
UD(0,1)	0.051	0.44
UD(1,2)	0.051	0.46

Table 2: Impact of selection bias effect $\eta = 0.09$ with $\sigma = 0.73$ on probability of type I error for different randomization procedures

Randomization Procedure [<i>RP</i>]	Type I Error Probability [mean]	$P_{RP}(\omega \leq 0.05)$
CR	0.050	0.47
RAR	0.052	0.12
PBR(2)	0.107	0.00
PBR(10)	0.071	0.00
BSD(3)	0.055	0.00
BSD(4)	0.053	0.10
BSD(5)	0.052	0.23
MP(3)	0.064	0.00
MP(4)	0.059	0.00
MP(5)	0.056	0.00
EBC(0.67)	0.064	0.00
CHEN(2, 0.67)	0.074	0.00
CHEN(3, 0.67)	0.068	0.00
CHEN(4, 0.67)	0.065	0.00
CHEN(5, 0.67)	0.064	0.00
UD(0,1)	0.052	0.23
UD(1,2)	0.052	0.26

Table 3: Impact of linear time trend effect $\theta = 0.26$ with $\sigma = 0.73$ on probability of type I error for different randomization procedures

Randomization Procedure [<i>RP</i>]	Type I Error Probability [mean]	$P_{RP}(\omega \leq 0.05)$
CR	0.050	0.67
RAR	0.050	0.66
PBR(2)	0.049	1.00
PBR(10)	0.049	1.00
BSD(3)	0.049	1.00
BSD(4)	0.049	0.99
BSD(5)	0.049	0.95
MP(3)	0.049	1.00
MP(4)	0.049	1.00
MP(5)	0.049	1.00
EBC(0.67)	0.049	0.99
CHEN(2, 0.67)	0.049	1.00
CHEN(3, 0.67)	0.049	1.00
CHEN(4, 0.67)	0.049	1.00
CHEN(5, 0.67)	0.049	1.00
UD(0,1)	0.050	0.81
UD(1,2)	0.050	0.81

Table 4: Impact of selection bias effect $\eta = 0.09$ and linear time trend effect $\theta = 0.26$ with $\sigma = 0.73$ on probability of type I error for Big Stick with varying MTI

Randomization Procedure [<i>RP</i>]	Type I Error Probability [mean]	$P_{RP}(\omega \leq 0.05)$
BSD(10)	0.050	0.53
BSD(15)	0.051	0.51
BSD(20)	0.050	0.52
BSD(25)	0.050	0.53
BSD(30)	0.050	0.53
BSD(35)	0.050	0.53
BSD(40)	0.050	0.52

Table 5: Impact of selection bias effect $\eta = 0.09$ with $\sigma = 0.73$ on probability of type I error for Big Stick with varying MTI

Randomization Procedure [<i>RP</i>]	Type I Error Probability [mean]	$P_{RP}(\omega \leq 0.05)$
BSD(10)	0.051	0.41
BSD(15)	0.050	0.45
BSD(20)	0.050	0.46
BSD(25)	0.050	0.47
BSD(30)	0.050	0.47
BSD(35)	0.050	0.47
BSD(40)	0.050	0.47

Table 6: Impact of linear time trend effect $\theta = 0.26$ with $\sigma = 0.73$ on probability of type I error for Big Stick with varying MTI

Randomization Procedure [<i>RP</i>]	Type I Error Probability [mean]	$P_{RP}(\omega \leq 0.05)$
BSD(10)	0.050	0.69
BSD(15)	0.050	0.65
BSD(20)	0.050	0.66
BSD(25)	0.050	0.66
BSD(30)	0.050	0.67
BSD(35)	0.050	0.67
BSD(40)	0.050	0.67

Table 7: Impact of selection bias effect $\eta = 0.09$ and linear time trend effect $\theta = 0.26$ with $\sigma = 0.73$ on probability of type I error for various Wei's Urn Designs

Randomization Procedure [<i>RP</i>]	Type I Error Probability [mean]	$P_{RP}(\omega \leq 0.05)$
UD(0,1)	0.051	0.44
UD(0,2)	0.051	0.44
UD(0,3)	0.051	0.44
UD(1,1)	0.051	0.47
UD(1,2)	0.051	0.46
UD(1,3)	0.051	0.45
UD(2,1)	0.051	0.48
UD(2,2)	0.051	0.47
UD(2,3)	0.051	0.46

Table 8: Impact of selection bias effect $\eta = 0.09$ and with $\sigma = 0.73$ on probability of type I error for various Wei's Urn Designs

Randomization Procedure [<i>RP</i>]	Type I Error Probability [mean]	$P_{RP}(\omega \leq 0.05)$
UD(0,1)	0.052	0.23
UD(0,2)	0.052	0.24
UD(0,3)	0.052	0.23
UD(1,1)	0.051	0.28
UD(1,2)	0.052	0.26
UD(1,3)	0.052	0.26
UD(2,1)	0.051	0.30
UD(2,2)	0.051	0.28
UD(2,3)	0.051	0.27

Table 9: Impact of linear time trend effect $\theta = 0.26$ with $\sigma = 0.73$ on probability of type I error for various Wei's Urn Designs

Randomization Procedure [<i>RP</i>]	Type I Error Probability [mean]	$P_{RP}(\omega \leq 0.05)$
UD(0,1)	0.050	0.81
UD(0,2)	0.050	0.81
UD(0,3)	0.050	0.81
UD(1,1)	0.050	0.80
UD(1,2)	0.050	0.81
UD(1,3)	0.050	0.80
UD(2,1)	0.050	0.79
UD(2,2)	0.050	0.80
UD(2,3)	0.050	0.80